

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. Employee retention is a crucial factor for company sustainability and success, especially in competitive industries such as the energy sector. The research method used is a quantitative approach with data collection techniques through questionnaires. The research sample consisted of 50 employees of PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring who were selected using the saturated sample method. The results showed that talent management and job satisfaction partially affect employee retention, while career development has no positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. Simultaneously, talent management, job satisfaction, and career development variables have a positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. From the results of multiple linear regression tests, the adjusted R-square value is 66.5%, so it can be explained that 66.5% of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development variables affect employee retention, while the remaining 33.5% is influenced by other variables. Talent management was found to be the most influential factor, followed by job satisfaction and career development. This finding implies that companies need to focus on effective talent management strategies, improve employee job satisfaction, and provide clear career development opportunities to improve employee retention.

Keywords: Talent Management; Job Satisfaction; Career Development; Employee Retention

1. Introduction

Employees are a crucial asset for construction companies, acting as the main driver in realizing quality and innovative projects. All processes in a company or organization will not be able to run well if the organization does not have or lacks human resources in carrying out a process in the organization [1]. Their technical expertise, field experience, and adaptability to the latest technology determine the success of each project. Retaining quality employees is a top priority, given the high recruitment and training costs and the importance of maintaining continuity of knowledge and corporate culture. Effective employee retention not only increases productivity and efficiency, but also builds a solid team, improves morale, and strengthens the company's reputation in the eyes of clients and business partners. Employee Retention according to [2] is the ability of a company to retain potential employees that the company has to remain loyal to the company. The goal is to retain employees who are considered qualified in the company.

According to [3] the effort to retain employees is a process carried out by the company to create an atmosphere that keeps employees motivated to be in the organization, and is beneficial for both parties, companies and employees. The problem that arises when mismanaging human resources is a decrease in employee performance [4]. But in general, the relationship between employee retention and performance can be complex and it is proven that performance can decrease if employee retention will have a bad impact and there is a possibility that there will be employee stagnation if turnover is too low (Al-Sharafi et al., 2018)..

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[6] state that talent management strategies have an influence on employee retention. [7] state that every organization needs employees who are skilled at doing their jobs, so effective human resource management is needed. This is not only necessary to improve employee skills, but also so that employees feel comfortable working in the organization, which in turn will have an impact on increasing employee engagement and retention. [8] defines talent management as a concept that starts from how to plan, obtain, develop, and retain talent in an organization or company. Attracting as many talented employees as possible and keeping them in the workplace for the long term is the key to winning business competition (Ratnawati & Subudi, 2018)..

Another factor that can affect employee retention is job satisfaction [10]. According to [11] Job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behavior towards their work through an assessment of one of the jobs as a sense of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of work. Satisfaction can describe the positive and negative feelings of employees towards the work they face, such as the feeling of achieving success at work, implementing high satisfaction with employees who feel happy and comfortable with the conditions of the organizational environment and getting rewards for their efforts [12] in research [13]. Individuals who are satisfied with their work will have a high commitment to the company and the desire to leave the company will be lower [14].

According to [15] employee retention can be influenced by career development. Career development plays an important role in the organization, which will lead to an increase in employees' intention to leave the organization [16]. According to [17] career is a personal improvement that a person makes to achieve a career plan and an improvement by the personnel department to achieve a work plan according to the path or level of the organization. Career development can be carried out if the company can openly provide opportunities for employees to develop their careers [13]. Career development is used as personal improvements made by a person to achieve a career plan. The lack of support from the company will hinder the career progress of employees, the personality of employees who are not proactive in the company, the lack of training opportunities and employee development is likely to be the cause of problems in employee career development.

The development of the construction sector in Indonesia continues to show a significant increase, driven by the growth of national infrastructure such as the construction of toll roads, airports, and industrial estates. This sector plays a vital role in supporting economic recovery and attracting investment. PT Nusantara Power Engineering Medan, as a construction company, plays an active role in strategic projects that strengthen the infrastructure ecosystem in the North Sumatra region. In the midst of intense industry competition, the company's success is highly dependent on the quality of its competent and professional Human Resources (HR). Excellent human resources are proven to maximize performance by ensuring smooth projects, operational efficiency, and client satisfaction. The company's success is highly dependent on the quality of Human Resources (HR) and employee performance. Therefore, retaining excellent employees is a top priority, which requires an in-depth understanding of the factors that influence retention. Talent management, job satisfaction, and career development are key elements in creating a productive work environment, because these three aspects not only improve performance, but also build employee loyalty in the long run, so that companies can continue to compete and grow amidst industry challenges. Therefore, this research will raise the title "The Effect of Talent Management, Job Satisfaction, and Career Development on Employee Retention of PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring".

2. Literature Review

2.1. Employee Retention

An organization is a collection of people who have different competencies, who are interdependent on one another, who strive to realize their common interests, by utilizing various resources. Basically, the common goal that the organization wants to realize is to make a profit. Therefore, employees who have high performance are needed. The definition of employee retention is a necessity that needs to be done by the company in order to maintain the best human resources (HR) it has. The definition of employee retention is an effort to retain employees in a company as a key expert.

Employee Retention according to [2] is the ability of the company to retain potential employees owned by the company to remain loyal to the company. The goal is to retain employees who are considered qualified in the company.

Employee retention is an organizational effort to retain existing employees within the company or organization for a longer period of time [18]. Retention aims to create a positive relationship between employees and the organization, so that employees feel satisfied and have the motivation to keep working in that place. With increased employee retention, companies can reduce costs associated with employee turnover and retain valuable knowledge and experience within the organization [19].

2.2. Talent Management

The real competition between organizations is not in the market (not in the market), but in the head (but in the brain). Competition is not in the product, but in the mindset. This is the talent war era. In any process, whether manufacturing or services, both are done by humans. It is people who determine the quality of the process, determine the quality of products and services, determine the perception of quality in the eyes of consumers, and determine market share.

Talent is an employee in an organization or company who is able to have an above-average influence through the achievement of good performance and ownership of potential that can affect the short and long term development of the organization, the talent in question is at a level that applies to all functions and groups within the organization or company [20]. Talent management can exist and experience development because of the phenomenon of the war for talent in companies in America in 1997, many organizations are expected to experience difficulties in being able to maintain the best resources, as well as experiencing difficulties in the recruitment process of potential and highly skilled employee candidates due to increased competition and providing limited candidates [21].

“Talent Management is a process to ensure the company's ability to fill key positions of future leaders and positions that support the company's core Talent Management (unique skills and high strategic value).” [8] defines that talent management is a concept that starts from how to plan, obtain, develop, and retain talent in an organization or company.

2.3. Job Satisfaction

Human resources need to get the main attention so that the company can achieve predetermined goals. One way that can be done to pay attention to employee needs is to pay attention to employee job satisfaction [22]. Job satisfaction is a feeling that a person feels about himself and his job [22]. According to [11] Job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behavior towards their work through an assessment of one of the jobs as a sense of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of work. [23] defines job satisfaction as a pleasant or positive emotional state derived from an assessment of one's work or job experience.

Then [24] say that job satisfaction is a positive feeling about work, which results from an evaluation of its characteristics. According to [25] job satisfaction is a person's thoughts, feelings and action tendencies which are a person's attitude towards work. People with high job satisfaction have positive feelings about their jobs, and people with low job satisfaction have negative feelings about their jobs. Job satisfaction will always be an issue for companies.

2.4. Career Development

According to [26] Career Development is a job or position that a person has (or holds) during his working life. That careers show the development of individual employees in the level of position / rank that can be achieved while working in an organization. Meanwhile, career development according to [27] is personal improvements made to achieve a career plan. According to [28] career development is the process of increasing individual work abilities achieved in order to achieve the desired career.

According to [17] a career is a personal improvement that a person makes to achieve a career plan and an improvement by the personnel department to achieve a work plan in accordance with the path or level of the organization. So no matter how good a career plan that has been made by a worker is accompanied by a reasonable and realistic career goal, the plan will not become a reality without systematic and programmatic career development. According to [29] that career development is an increase in the position of employees in the company in a predetermined professional path to improve their performance.

According to [30] Career development is a lifelong process that includes various work roles (paid and unpaid). It is carried out throughout life, such as daily life roles (parents, volunteers), leisure activities, study and work. It is the idea of development both in the workplace and at a personal level, embracing the idea of lifelong learning and skills development.

2.4.1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the theories that have been put forward, the relationship between job satisfaction and workload can be presented in the form of a conceptual framework which is described in the form of a chart as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

3. Material and methods

This research uses quantitative research, meaning research that emphasizes its analysis on numeric data (numbers) processed by statistical methods. When associated with this study, it can be explained that the first variable (independent variable), namely audio-visual media, is expected to cause or affect the second variable (dependent variable), namely learning outcomes. The sampling technique used is non probability sampling, namely saturated sampling technique with a population of 50 employees of PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring.

Based on the source, the data used in this study are primary data such as the results of interviews with several employees of PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. Then Secondary data is in the form of company documentation, reference books, and other information related to the research. Data collection was carried out by means of interviews and questionnaires related to employee retention. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression which is obtained with the SPSS version 29 application. Before the multiple linear regression test is carried out, a research instrument test is carried out in the form of validity and reliability tests, as well as a classical assumption test consisting of normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The results of the descriptive statistical analysis in the study for each variable can be seen in the following table:

Table 1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Talent Management	50	16	25	20.04	1.906
Job Satisfaction	50	13	20	16.26	1.536
Career Development	50	12	25	20.44	2.957
Employee Retention	50	16	30	24.00	3.057
Valid N (listwise)	50				

Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on the table, the minimum value of the talent management variable is 16, the maximum value is 25, the mean value is 20.04 and the std value. deviation of 1.906. The minimum value of the job satisfaction variable was 13, the maximum value was 20, the mean value was 16.26 and the std value. deviation of 1.536. The minimum value of the career development variable is 12, the maximum value is 25, the mean value is 20.44 and the std value. deviation of

2.957. The minimum value of the employee retention variable is 16, the maximum value is 30, the mean value is 24.00 and the std value. deviation of 3.057.

4.2. Classical Assumption Test

4.2.1. Normality Test

[31] states that the normality test aims to test whether in the regression model, the perturbing or residual variables have a normal distribution. The normality test used in this study is the normality of p-plot and Kolmogorov Smirnov presented in the data below:

Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Figure 2 P-Plot Normality Test Results

Table 2 Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
			Unstandardized Residual
N			50
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean		0.0000000
	Std. Deviation		1.71518164
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute		0.110
	Positive		0.062
	Negative		-0.110
Test Statistic			0.110
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c			0.177
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^d	Sig.		0.128
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0.119
		Upper Bound	0.137

a. Test distribution is Normal; b. Calculated from data; c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.; d. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed 2000000.; Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on figure 2. Above it can be seen that the existing points are close to the diagonal line. If the distribution of residual data is normal, then the line describing the actual data will follow its diagonal line. Thus it can be concluded that the

distribution of residual data is normal. The next residual normality test is by using a statistical test using the kolmogorov-smirnof test, by looking at the kolmogorov and Asymp.Sig values which can be seen in table 2.

Judging from Table 2., it can be seen that Kolmogorov-Smirnov with the value of Asymp.sig. 0.137 is greater than 0.05, so this regression model is suitable for further analysis.

4.2.2. *Multicollinearity Test*

This test was carried out with the aim of finding out whether a regression model found a correlation between independent variables. states that independent variables must be free from the symptoms of multicollinearity. Regression is stated to be non-multicollinearity if the VIF<10 value and tolerance value >0.1 then multicollinearity does not occur.[31]

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficientsa			
Type		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Talent Management	0.390	2.566
	Job Satisfaction	0.390	2.562
	Career Development	0.628	1.591

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Retention; Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on table 3, the multicollinearity test above can be seen that there is no multicollinearity between the free variables because the results of the calculation of the tolerance value are greater than 0.01 and the VIF value is <10.

4.2.3. *Heteroscedasticity Test*

This test is one of the classic assumption tests that must be performed on linear regression. This test is to find out if there is a deviation from the classical assumption conditions in linear regression, where in the regression model the condition of the absence of heteroscedasticity must be met. The heteroscedasticity test uses scatterplot graphs and glacier tests. The basis for decision-making for the glacier test is that if the probability value (significance) is less than 0.05, then heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Figure 3 Heteroscedasticity – Scatterplot

From Figure 3. It can be seen that the dots are randomly spread and scattered both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis.

Table 4 Glejser Test Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Type		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.785	1.828		2.071	0.044
	Talent Management	-0.136	0.136	-0.229	-0.996	0.324
	Job Satisfaction	-0.047	0.169	-0.064	-0.279	0.781
	Career Development	0.048	0.069	0.125	0.693	0.492

a. Dependent Variable: ABRESID; Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test through the Glejser test in table 4 above, it can be seen that sig. in each variable the value is more than 0.05. And it can be said that this shows that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model in this study.

4.3. Multiple Linear Regression

According to Ghozali (2018), in regression analysis, in addition to measuring the strength of the relationship between two or more variables, it also shows the direction of the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables.

Table 5 Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Type		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.761	2.853		-0.968	0.338
	Talent Management	0.564	0.213	0.352	2.656	0.011
	Job Satisfaction	0.487	0.264	0.245	1.849	0.071
	Career Development	0.368	0.108	0.356	3.413	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Retention Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on the table of the results of the multiple linear regression analysis above, the following equation is obtained:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

$$\text{Employee Retention} = -2.761 + 0.564X_1 + 0.487X_2 + 0.368X_3$$

Judging from the equation above, it can be explained as follows:

Based on the multiple linear regression equation above, it is known that the constant value is -2,761, meaning that if the variables of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development are considered constant, then employee retention can be predicted to be -2,761 units.

The talent management regression coefficient of 0.564 is a positive value, meaning that every increase in one talent management unit will increase employee retention by 0.564 with the assumption of other variables constant.

The regression coefficient of job satisfaction of 0.487 has a positive value, meaning that every increase in one unit of job satisfaction will increase employee retention by 0.487 with the assumption of other variables constant.

The career development regression coefficient of 0.368 is a positive value, meaning that every increase in one career development unit will increase employee retention by 0.368 with the assumption of other variables constant.

Test Goodness of Fit

4.3.1. Test T (partial)

The t-statistical test basically shows how far an independent variable partially influences the variation of dependent variables. In this study, a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$) was used. If the t-count < the t-table, then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable (hypothesis rejected). Meanwhile, if the t-count > the t-table, then the independent variable partially affects the dependent variable (hypothesis is accepted).

Table 6 Test Results t (Partial)

Coefficients a						
Type		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.761	2.853		-0.968	0.338
	Talent Management	0.564	0.213	0.352	2.656	0.011
	Job Satisfaction	0.487	0.264	0.245	1.849	0.071
	Career Development	0.368	0.108	0.356	3.413	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Retention Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

The t-table value is $df-k = 50-4$, which is 46 with a t-table magnitude of 2.01290 with an α (α) value of 5% (0.05). Based on table 6 above, the results of the research for the t test are as follows:

- Hypothesis 1 states that talent management variables affect employee retention. Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, it shows the value of $t\text{-calculating} > t\text{-table}$ ($2.656 > 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.011 < 0.05$ so that it can be concluded that **H1 is accepted**, which means that partially the talent management variable has a positive and significant effect on employee retention of PT Nusantara Power Engineering.
- Hypothesis 2 states that the job satisfaction variable has an effect on employee retention. Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, it shows the value of $t\text{-calculating} < t\text{-table}$ ($1.849 < 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.071 > 0.05$ so that it can be concluded that **H2 is rejected**, which means that partially the job satisfaction variable does not have a positive and significant effect on employee retention of PT Nusantara Power Engineering.
- Hypothesis 3 states that career development variables have an effect on employee retention. Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, it shows the value of $t\text{-calculating} > t\text{-table}$ ($3.413 > 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$ so that it can be concluded that **H3 is accepted**, which means that partially the career development variable has a positive and significant effect on employee retention of PT Nusantara Power Engineering.

4.3.2. Test F (Simultaneous)

The F test is used to test the independent variables together against the bound variables. The test was carried out using a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$). If the significance > 0.05, it means that together the independent variables do not have a significant influence on the dependent variables.

Table 7 Test Result F (Simultaneous)

ANOVA a						
Type		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	313.849	3	104.616	33.384	0.001b
	Residual	144.151	46	3.134		
	Total	458.000	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Retention b. Predictors: (Constant), Career Development, Job Satisfaction, Talent Management Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

From table 7. Above it can be seen that with a significant number of 0.001, which is less than 0.05 or ($0.001 < 0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that the variables of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on employee retention of PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring.

4.3.3. R2 Test (Determination)

The determination coefficient (Adjusted R2) is a coefficient that shows the percentage of influence of all dependent variables on dependent variables. This percentage shows how much independent variables can explain dependent variables. The greater the determination coefficient, the better the independent variable is in explaining the dependent variable.

Table 8 Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Model Summaryb				
Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.828a	0.685	0.665	1.770

a. Predictors: (Constant), Career Development, Job Satisfaction, Talent Management b. Dependent Variable: Employee Retention Source: SPSS data processing 29., 2024

Based on table 8, the results of the determination coefficient (R2) test above show an Adjusted R Square (R2) value of 0.665. This shows that the dependent variable of employee retention can be explained by the variables of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development by 66.5%, while by 33.5% influenced by other variables outside of this study.

5. Discussion

5.1. Talent management affects employee retention

Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, the t-count > t-table value ($2.656 > 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.011 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that talent management has a positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. The interpretation of the research results states that there is a substantial and statistically significant positive effect of talent management practices on the company's ability to retain its employees. In real context, this means that PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring's efforts in developing, nurturing, and managing its employees' talents have proven effective in increasing employees' loyalty and desire to remain with the company. This finding confirms the importance of a proper talent management strategy as a key tool in maintaining human resource stability and reducing employee turnover in the company.

5.2. Job satisfaction affects employee retention

Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, the t-count value < t-table ($1.849 < 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.071 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that job satisfaction does not have a positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Enjiniring. Job satisfaction is not only determined by salary, benefits, career development opportunities, corporate culture, and work-life balance also play an important role. What makes an employee satisfied today may not be enough to keep him satisfied tomorrow. Changes in team dynamics, workload, or even personal factors outside of work can affect one's level of job satisfaction. Therefore, while companies strive to

increase job satisfaction, this may not always result in increased employee retention. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs may instead look for new opportunities. This could be because they feel they have peaked in their current position and are looking for new challenges for their personal and professional growth. High satisfaction in their current job gives them the confidence to seek better opportunities elsewhere.

5.3. Career development affects employee retention

Based on the results of the t-count statistical test, the t-count > t-table value ($3.413 > 2.01290$) with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that career development has a positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Engineering. This means that PT Nusantara Power Engineering's efforts in providing good career development opportunities, such as training programs, promotions, or job rotations, have proven effective in increasing employee loyalty and reducing turnover rates. This result confirms the importance of human resource development strategy as a tool to retain the best talent in the organization.

5.4. Talent management, job satisfaction, and career development simultaneously affect employee retention

Based on the statistical test results, it can be seen that the significant number is 0.001, which is smaller than 0.05 or ($0.001 < 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the variables of talent management, job satisfaction, and career development together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on employee retention at PT Nusantara Power Engineering. This indicates that there is a need for an employee retention strategy that includes a structured talent development program, initiatives to increase job satisfaction through improving the work environment and reward system, and transparent and equitable career planning. By implementing a strategy that accommodates these three aspects simultaneously, the company can improve its ability to retain quality employees, which in turn will support the sustainability and competitiveness of the company in the long term.

6. Conclusion

- Implement a Talent Management Program based on individual performance and potential by mapping employees using methods such as a 9-box grid to identify talents, then focus on promotions and strategic projects on high-potential employees. Furthermore, develop internal talent through job rotation programs, cross-departmental project assignments, and mentoring by senior managers.
- Implement a work-life balance policy with flexible or hybrid work schedules for non-technical employees, and provide additional leave for high-intensity projects. Ensure a safe working environment through periodic inspections and provide health facilities in field projects. Organizes regular town hall sessions and job satisfaction surveys to understand employee aspirations and address problems before they develop. These measures will help reduce burnout, increase productivity, and create a better work environment for all employees.
- To improve employee career development, companies should implement training and certification programs that are relevant to the industry, accompanied by a clear and transparent career plan. Develop a measurable career path and communicate openly to each employee through one-on-one sessions with managers, including periodic performance evaluations. Make sure promotions are based on achievement and competency to motivate employees in developing themselves

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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